

Optimization of Alloy Wheel Rim by Using CFD Analysis

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Abstract— The purpose of a car wheel rim is to provide a firm base to hold the tire. The rim design is an important industrial activity that influences the quality of the product. The present work deals with a newly designed wheel rim to the analysis of equivalent maximum stresses in medium weight vehicles which have a wide range of scope for research for its improved performance and application. In particular, decisions related to the sizing of the wheel rim, to the number and type of spokes and to the spokes structural layout are addressed. The process relies on the combination of a simplified finite element model of the tire/wheel assembly and artificial neural networks used for global approximation, within a multi-objective optimization framework.

I. Introduction

The rim of a wheel is that circular part of the steel on which the interior fringe of the tire is installed. Major characteristic of the rim is to assist and seal the tire to the wheel. It guarantees the right becoming between tire and rim and retains air inside the tubeless tire. A general steel wheel is synthetic through a square metal sheet. The metal sheet is folded in cylindrical shape with two edges of the sleeve welded collectively at the end. To attain a given thickness profile of the sleeve at the least one cylindrical float spinning operation is finished. To support the cylindrical rim structure disc is synthetic through stamping a metal plate. Suitable holes for the center hub and lugs are furnished in to the disc.

Type of Wheel Rim

Mainly steel and some light alloys are used for normal wheels but some composite materials including glass-fiber are being used for special wheels as mentioned below:

- Wire Spoke wheel
 Cord wheels, wire-spoked wheels, tension-spoked wheels, or "suspension" wheels are wheels whose rims hook up with their hubs by using cord spokes. despite the fact that those wires are generally stiffer than an ordinary twine rope, they characteristic routinely similar to tensioned flexible wires, preserving the rim genuine whilst helping implemented masses.

Fig 1 Wire spoke wheel

Steel disc wheel are spoke less vehicular wheel, mainly on cars, having a heavy round pressed-metal disk established at the wheel hub and supporting the tire rim on its periphery.

Fig 2 Steel disc wheel

- Light Alloy wheel-
 Alloy wheels are aluminum or magnesium alloy wheels. alloys are mixtures of metals and other factors. They generally offer greater strength than pure metals, which are generally much softer and more ductile. alloys of aluminium or magnesium are normally lighter for the identical strength, provide better heat conduction, and frequently produce improved cosmetic appearance over steel wheels.

Even though steel, the most common material used in wheel manufacturing, is an alloy of iron and carbon, the time period "alloy wheel" is generally reserved for wheels Made from non-ferrous alloys.

Fig. 3 Alloy wheel

These are further classified as

1. Aluminum Alloy wheel
2. Magnesium Alloy wheel
3. Titanium Alloy wheel
4. Composite Material wheel

II. Literature Review

Sunil N. Yadav (2023) examines the impact of the camber angle on the stress distribution and fatigue life of a car's rim under radial load conditions due to the relief and bumps. The finite element analysis (FEA) is completed by simulating the test conditions to analyze the stress distribution and durability of the car's steel rim. In particular, the calculations of the experimental life of a wheel rim are compared with the predictions of a finite element analysis.

Prof. N. S. Hanamapure (2021) The influence of the slip angle on the stress distribution and the duration of the rim of a car under radial load conditions, which occur due to fields outside the road and rough roads, should be studied. Finite element analysis (FEA) is performed by simulating test situations in order to analyze the stress distribution and the durability of a vehicle's steel wheel rim. Experimental analyzes that use a radial fatigue test system to evaluate fatigue duration affect the slip angle. The radial fatigue test uses the SAE J328 standard. This exercise, recommended by SAE, provides for minimum performance requirements and standard procedures for fatigue tests on bicycles destined for normal road traffic and for short use in cars. In particular, the calculations of the experimental life of a wheel rim are compared with the predictions of a finite element analysis.

KalpeshR.Salunkhe et al. (2019) Wheel is a main mechanical term of the vehicular suspension system that supports the static and dynamic loads encountered during vehicle action. Since cars carry heavy loads of occupants as well as self-weight, the alloy wheel rim should be strong enough to withstand this load. Thus, their design should be done very cautiously. While designing such main kind of automotive component taking care of protection and cost are

very important concerns so that user can use it safely. Major five technical considerations while modelling any new alloy wheel rim are styling, aesthetic, mass, manufacturability and capability.

S.Ganesh (2017) Alloy wheels would be car wheels made from an aluminum or magnesium alloy, or sometimes a mixture of the two. The light alloy wheels are distinguished from the normal metal wheels by their low weight, which improves the steering and the speed of the vehicle. Currently, all four wheels are made of aluminium alloys. In this project, a parametric model for a light alloy rim used in a four-wheel vehicle is designed to collect data from the reverse engineering method of the current project. The design is evaluated by analyzing the model and converting the rim styles so that they are stable and balanced. The material must not deteriorate due to atmospheric agents and corrosion.

T. Siva Prasad (2014) It is considered a tire with a car rim, which belongs to the category of disc wheels. Design is an important industrial activity that affects product quality. The circle is modelled using the CATIA v5r17 modelling software. Using this software, the time required for the production of complex 3D models and the risk for the design and production process can be minimized in a simple way. The circle is modelled with CATIA. This CATIA modal is then imported into ANSYS for analysis.

Hongyu Wang (2013). The three-dimensional parametric version of the circle section is mainly based on solid parts. The finite element method is used to analyze stress and displacement distributions in a difficulty level of the rim with a variable section on the joint influence of radial load and inflation pressure. The optimization techniques, in which the multi-island genetic algorithm (MIGA) is mixed with the NLPQL algorithm, are used for exploration. High quality is optimized by defining the control parameters for the shape of the circle. The results show that the optimization effect is good.

Ch. P. V. Ravi Kumar (2013) This analysis includes the zero plastic deformation that is activated during the impact test. Topology optimization is completed by increasing the rim thickness until the plastic elongation value is less than 4%. The main objective of the project is the creation of a finite element model (hexa and penta elements) using Hyper Mesh 10.0 with all the properties, materials, loads and limit situations that must be designated as special by the customer. Impact analysis is performed using LS-Dyna software to predict plastic deformation during the impact test. The topology is optimized by changing the thickness of the die-cast aluminum wheel rim until the plastic deformation value is less than 4.0%.

Liangmo Wang (2011) The fatigue life of the aluminium wheels has been replaced by that foreseen on the basis of the amplitude of the equivalent deformation and the S-N curve of the aluminium alloy rim. The results of the aluminium wheel fatigue test bench show that the reference wheel failed the test and that its crack opening passed into the cavity of the hub bolt corresponding to the simulation. Using the method proposed in this article, the wheel life cycle has increased to over 1.0×10^5 and has met the design

requirements. The result showed that the proposed approach to integrate finite element analysis and the nominal stress method is a good effective method for predicting the fatigue life of aluminium wheels.

Haruyukikonishi(2009) implemented a method for impact strength estimation of the automotive wheel has been developed based totally on static FEM analysis and simplified dynamic analysis the use of a mass-spring system. aluminium disk wheels were analyzed the analytical results show good agreement with result of the impact test of the forged aluminium disk wheel. in addition, effect tests of cast aluminium disk wheel have been performed. in this case, the failure at the compressive side of the spoke was observed. the mechanism of this kind of failure was discussed based on the results strain measurement

III. Objective

IV.

The primary objective of the present work to search an alloy material that has strength and effective as conventional. To implement a material in vehicle wheel rim that can overcome the various problems. Use of a material that is lighter than any other alloy wheel material and can lead to the overall weight reduction of the vehicle and will further decrease the deformation.

V. Methodology

Modelling in CATIA V5

To carry out the static analysis on wheel a 3D model is designed using the CATIA V5R20 designing software.

Fig 4 - 3D model of Wheel

Meshing of Geometry Meshing is defined the process of dividing the whole component into wide variety of elements in order that each time the boundary conditions are applied at the component it distributes the inputs uniformly referred to as meshing. The mesh created on this is shown in figure

The total node is generated 11275 & total no. of elements is 5667 for wheel geometry.

Fig 5 Meshing of Wheel

Material Properties

Here in this study the test is carried out with different alloys materials of Al and carbon fiber. Various properties of the materials are mentioned below.

Table Properties of Material used

S.No	Material	Young's Modulus (EX)(MPa)	Poisson's Ratio (PRXY)	Density(Kg /m ³)	Shear Modulus (MPa)
1	Hard Drawn Spring Steel	2.76x10 ⁵	0.35	2712	26000
2	Carbon Fiber	1.23 x10 ⁵	0.282	1400	47972
3	Titanium Alloy	9.6 x10 ¹⁰	0.36	4620	35924

Static Analysis

Stress and deformation produced in the wheel is calculated after carrying out the static analysis on the wheel. The simulation is carried out after applying the load of 0.0428Mpa on the surface of wheel rim.

A. Equivalent Von-misses stress

Fig 6: Equivalent von-misses stress for Al alloy

Fig 7: Equivalent von-misses stress for Carbon Fiber

Fig 8: Equivalent von-misses stress for Titanium Alloy

RESULTS

Case-1:- Analysis with tyre inflation pressure 200 Kpa and radial load of 150 kg.

Aluminum Material

Fig 9. Total Deformation in aluminum
In figure , total deformations are found with Aluminum as the material on the wheel. The maximum deformation is $4.08 \times 10^{-5}m$.

Carbon Fiber Material

Fig 10. Life cycle in carbon fiber
The life cycle of Carbon fiber wheel is 1×10^{10}

Epoxy material

Fig.11 Equivalent stress in epoxy

In figure equivalent stresses is found with Epoxy as the material on the wheel. The maximum equivalent stress is $6.21 \times 10^6 \text{ Pa}$. and minimum stress is $7.5752 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}$.

Graph 1 -Equivalent stress at 200Kpa

Graph 2 -Total deformation at 200Kpa

Graph 3 -equivalent stress at 280Kpa

Graph 4 -Equivalent at 280Kpa

VI. Conclusion

- Carbon fiber is subjected to maximum equivalent stress compared to aluminum and E-poxy under radial loading of 200 kg. Whereas, E-poxy has the minimum stress under radial load of 225 kg.
- Life cycle of E-poxy is lower than Carbon fiber and aluminum. Lower life cycle means lower performance rate.
- E-poxy is subjected to maximum equivalent stress under all radial loading conditions, i.e. 150kg, 175kg, 200kg, and 225kg, whereas aluminum has the minimum stress under all the radial load conditions.
- Deformation in all the three materials is same i.e. aluminum, carbon fiber and E-poxy and is maximum under 150kg radial load condition. Whereas minimum deformation is same for all the three materials and it is under 225 kg radial load condition.

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